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Principal's message

Dr. Rajul Gajjar, Principal, L.D.College of Engineering

L. D. College of Engineering has been pioneer in Engineering education. L.D.C.E. offers 14 undergraduate courses and 17 post graduate courses. The campus nurtures technologically sound engineers with high values as future professionals. L.D.College of Engineering has created an ecosystem that helps students innovate and experiment with new ideas.

To promote R & D, the college has created central facilities of Design Lab, DST IT Incubator, Centre of Excellence Welding, Centre of Excellence Siemens, ISRO NAVIC Satellite Communication Receiver, Supercomputer Lab and SSIP Cell for students and teachers. All departments have project grants from GUJCOST, AICTE, DST and SSIP. Recent Start-ups such as Exposit, Reolo, Trauma Patch have received National and International awards. 110 innovative Projects are funded under SSIP. College has filled 36 Patents in different areas. Research activities such as this conference, pave the way for the advancements. We at L.D.C.E. are highly focused on research and hence this platform for the research community to interact and exchange the ideas. I extend my best wishes to the authors, organizers and all those who are participating at the conference. This 2ND edition of National conference on "Research Trends in Information & Communication Technology", will be beneficial to all participants in terms of learning experience and sharing experience. Key note addresses from eminent professors and research scientists, paper presentation in different domains will enhance the knowledge and networking among researchers and will help the participants immensely in their research career. Once again I extend my pleasure in welcoming all the participants and convey my best wishes for NCRTICT-2020.

Message - Head (Information Technology Department)

Information Technology Department works with the vision of imparting sustainable technical knowledge and also believes in enrichment of social and ethical values. The department always believes in exploring the knowledge beyond syllabus. Every new idea is nurtured here and the path for idea to implementation is provided so that every virtual idea gets physical shape.

The organization of 2ND edition of National conference on “Research Trends in Information & Communication Technology” is a step in the direction to provide a platform where industry, research institutes and academics collaborate and construct projects, processes, theories that are beneficial to the society and nation. When the whole nation is working towards “Atmanirbhar Bharat”, this is a small pathway to ignite the minds of community.

The department is working on student start-ups, projects for undergraduates and dissertation work for post graduate students. Faculty members are working on research on the subject sign language for deaf and dumb, visual question answering for visually impaired, prediction of cyber crime. The students have taken up the projects such as app development for medical system, featuring products with virtual reality, identifying a person from photo album and a long list to mention.

I wish all the best to the participants of NCRTICT-2020. The experience that the participants are going to share and the experience that the participants are going to gain will pour the gap if any in completing the thought process. The conference will have an outcome that can be used on larger platform beneficial to all who are awaiting the solutions to the problems. The conference covers the different areas of research including machine learning, computer vision, image processing information security and all prominent areas on which the whole world is focusing. Once again, I wish, the best will be explored and best will be achieved. And above all, may the technology bring all the happiness and healthiness in the life of mankind.

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UNIMODAL TO MULTIMODAL EMOTION RECOGNITION: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

As Artificial intelligence is the fastest growing field for interdisciplinary research field in which computer science techniques can be implemented to solve the problems of social science. Emotion recognition is very challenging work as every person will express his/her emotion in different ways. The primary goal of this paper is to present the detailed study and critical analysis of existing unimodal recognition techniques like expression recognition from still images or video, audio expression recognition from available speech data, text expression from available social media post and psychological signals expression from EEG, EDA and ECG data. As unimodal emotion analysis is suffering from lower accuracy and lack of reliability, the multimodal emotion fusion is essential. This paper summarized the background of the multi modal fusion with existing data sets, feature extraction methods, different deep learning models they used and various fusion techniques like feature level or decision level.

Keywords: Emotion recognition, multimodal, fusion, Survey, Unimodal

DESIGN OF WHEELCHAIR FOR PHYSICALLY CHALLENGED PEOPLE BASED ON EYE MOVEMENT DETECTION USING IMAGE PROCESSING

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Abstract

The number of Paralysed or Physically handicapped people is increasing day by day. People who have the ability to move on their own are very valuable. However it is sometime difficult for a person with physical disability. They have lost their self-confidence. There are many wheelchairs available in the market but the proposed system present a low cost and real time solution so anyone can use it. The main objective of this system is to create wheelchair for physically handicapped people to move their wheelchair independently through the movement of eyes. The proposed system helps handicapped person to gain their self-confidence and will definitely help them to be a more independent. The proposed system initialized with camera. Viola-Jones algorithm is used for face detection. Eye movement is performed on MATLAB. MATLAB is communicating with PIC microcontroller using RF communication. PIC relays the control signal to L293D. L293D rotate the DC motor and direction display on LCD.

Keywords: Physically Handicapped People, Image Processing, MATLAB, RF Communication, PIC Controller, LCD, L293D Motor Driver, DC motor.

GUJARATI SPEECH RECOGNITION – A REVIEW

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Abstract

Automatic Speech Recognition is a techniques to determine human speech patterns, accordingly, relevant text output is obtained. Various interactive softwares are available in the market, however, due to vernacular languages the use of these softwares becomes limited as these software does not support all languages. In this paper we have reviewed Gujarati Speech Recognition System using different speech recognition methodologies which will cater the need of Gujarati users and will help them in technological advancement.

Keywords: Speech Recognition 1, Hidden Markov Model 2, Recurrent Neural Network 3, Deep Neural Network 4, End-to-End speech recognition 5

SOFTWARE DEFINED NETWORK: IMPORTANCE AND ISSUES

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Abstract

With the evolution of internet of things (IOT) almost every device is connected to internet. We are living in a digital society where huge amount of data is being generated due to technological innovations. Technologies like cloud computing generates large amount of data every second. Traditional IP networks were not designed to handle these types of rapid technological change. Managing traditional IP networks are becoming more complex due to the variety of data being generated by new technologies. Software-defined networking (SDN) is emerging as a promising technology that can change this complexity by separating the cores of traditional IP network: data planes and control planes. The separation will help to remove major barriers to new protocols and services. In this paper, we present a survey on Software-defined network and its major issues. We start with introducing motivation for SDN. Next, we present the basic architecture of SDN. We discuss major issues related to SDN and conclude discussion.

Keywords: Software-defined network, SDN, reliability, security

A REVIEW OF: SUBSTRATE INTEGRATED WAVEGUIDE BANDPASS FILTER FOR SATELLITE APPLICATION

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Abstract:

In modern wireless communication substrate integrated waveguide filters are used for high frequency application. This paper provides the review on Substrate Integrated Waveguide based microwave filter. Substrate integrated waveguide filter technology is implemented for satellite communication uplink and downlink frequency band. Design of substrate integrated waveguide filter can be used to improve various parameter of existing substrate integrated waveguide filter like size, return loss(S11), insertion loss(S21) etc.

Keywords: Satcom Application, Bandpass filter, Substrate Integrated Waveguide

REVIEW PAPER ON METAMATERIAL BASED SUPERSTRATE ANTENNA

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Abstract:

The aim in this paper is to review a new form of micro strip Patch antenna with metamaterial based superstrate inspired by an ordinary patch antenna resonating for various applications. It is shown that by implementing innovative resonators structure into the design, there is simultaneous gain and bandwidth improvement. The results in terms of gain, bandwidth, radiation pattern and return loss are analyzed in detail, which allows us to develop a comparative study according to the distance separating the superstrate placed in the antenna. In recent decade with the use of metamaterial based superstrate the size of antenna have been drastically reduce to very small sizes and light weight for actual practical application.

Keywords: Microstrip Patch, Metamaterial, SRR, CSRR, Superstrate.

REVIEW PAPER OF DGS BASED BAND PASS FILTER

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Abstract :

The modern wireless communication systems require dual bandpass filters that work at multiple frequency bands. This paper provides a review of the literature on DGS based microstrip Band Pass Filter. Band Pass Filter's features are low cost, compact dimensions, light weight and ground side a complete metallization structure.

In recent years, a new concept has been applied to the ground plane structure. This concept is known as the Defected Ground Structure. Using DGS improved the electrical performance in the pass band, sharps electivity, unwanted frequency rejection, and circuit size reduction. The results in terms of insertion loss and return loss are analyzed in detail, which comparative study according to base on DGS and without DGS filters.

Keywords:Microstrip Bandpass filter, Microstrip Hairpin bandpass filter, Defected ground structure.

VOLUME RENDERING FOR WEATHER DATA USING RAY-CASTING ALGORITHM ON WEB

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Abstract

Volume rendering is the key to visualize data in 3D. Ray-casting algorithm is a direct volume rendering technique that makes volume rendering possible. Applying the ray-casting algorithm to visualize weather data received by radars and satellites is a challenging problem. As radars and satellites receive large amounts of data in various formats it is necessary to find the data format compatible volume rendering. This paper represents the conversion of weather data formats and rendering of the data in 3D. Here, the ray-casting algorithm is implemented for visualization on a ray-casting based WebGL tool. Various features like, mapping textures with images, changing the range of dimensions, and colormap of volumetric data are added in results.

Keywords:Volume rendering, Ray-casting, Weather data, WebGL

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON SERVER CONSOLIDATION PROCESS IN CLOUD COMPUTING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Cloud computing is an on demand resources based computing model. This requires large amount of physical resources to provide services to the users on the basis of pay per usage model. So immoderate demand of cloud computing resources has been increase in computational power. Virtualization plays an important role in reducing energy consumption. Server consolidation approach involves gathering of several virtual machines into a single physical server. Server consolidation provides a better approach to save energy and to improve resource utilization in data centers, but the aggressive consolidation of virtual machines may lead to service-level agreement (SLAs) violations. It establishes the Quality of Service (QoS) agreed between service-based systems. Therefore, our goal is to minimize energy consumptions and reduces SLA violations. it is very meaningful to strike a tradeoff between energy efficient and reduction of SLA violations. This paper critically examines and discusses the various algorithms that use in server consolidation process and compare them on the basis of energy consumption and SLA violations.

Keywords: Cloud Computing, Virtualization, Server Consolidation, Energy efficient, SLA violations.

BIG DATA ANALYTICS SYSTEMFOR HEALTH CARE: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

Health is generating enormous volumes of data that can provide vital understandings into medical and real features of healthcare delivery. There is a general dearth of specific and combined health data analytics platforms that offer technical approaches to support the entire health data analysis channel. For example, health data selection, integration, inspection, visualization, and distribution. This paper reviews the numerous practical architectures of a health data analytics platform that offers a technical solution for analyzing big' health data originating from several sources with varied terminologies and plans. The present study which stresses the use of the enormous size of health information while merging multidimensional material from varied sources is discussed. Finally, a Research Gap is found in all studied technical architecture and probable solutions proposed.

Keywords:Big Data, Healthcare, Health informatics, Bighealth data, Hadoop, Data integration, Data standardization

A Survey on Online Advertising and Click fraud Detection

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Abstract—In today's scenario, web advertising has a very important role for promotion of any business through keywords. And due to this the capacity of click fraud to impact business models based on online advertisements emerged as a topic of discussion. Part of Google's financial success through the years was due to the rate per click online advertisement model; however, nowadays, this model has been heavily threatened by fraudulent clicks. Invalid clicks in advertisements, i.e., clicks that do not correspond to a real interest in the advertisement and deviate funds to scammers. One of the prominently used advertising model PPC(Pay Per Click) works by charging advertisers for each click on their advertisements or content as per the agreement. Among few styles of click-fraud, botnets and click-farm are the extreme ones. In order to solve this issue some solutions were presented. There are many techniques used for click-fraud analysis and detection, this paper is a survey that contemplates to showcase details related to click fraud and domains working on its detection

Keywords—Click Fraud, Pay-per-click, Online advertising, fraud analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

There have always been fraudsters in all walks of life, looking for easy ways to make money. Online advertising fraud offers the platform for malicious hackers with two reasons. One is that they can quickly ramp it up when they have a revenue generating working system, with almost no extra effort involved, so it gives them the ability to generate a lot of income. And we're talking about a lot here. The other factor is that the risk associated with punishment in digital ad fraud is relatively low, as online ad fraud falls within the jurisdiction's legal gray area and also does not involve physical risk compared to many other types of fraud. Ad fraud has become a topic of conversation over the past couple of years, with some studies claiming to be gradually decreasing and other studies claiming to have gone haywire. The real answer is probably that it's in the middle instead. Before the development of tools and analytics, ad fraud within digital advertising was predominated. Now, basic ad fraud often can be tackled with simple tools and analytics. Because of this, many companies consider the problem they are dealing with and do very little to protect themselves against the more lucrative and intelligent scams that now exist.

This paper provides overview on online advertising and click ad fraud, terminology relevant to it with different types of ad fraud and how security and fairness can be achieved. Later the paper discusses different click fraud solutions present and related research work with some implemented in the real world. Also how when applied this work and technologies could add security to the digital world if well explored.

II. OVERVIEW

• Technical terms

First of all, its important to mention some technical terms related to online advertising and click fraud[1].

- 1) Ad Click - The action taken either by clicking on ad with your mouse or by pressing enter when a user interacts with an ad.
- 2) Ad Fraud - The act of knowingly falsifying some commitment in online advertising.
- 3) Ad Injection - Inserting advertisements concealed in any online resource without authorization from the publisher of that site.
- 4) Ad Network - A service that connects advertisers and publishers to functions as a single point of contact between them.
- 5) Ad Exchange - A technology platform that enables the buyer and seller to interact from sources such as publishers and networks in online advertising.
- 6) Advertiser - An individual or organization that on the advertising platform tends to advertise their product.
- 7) Blacklisting - Lists of identified, excluded bad IPs and domains from the ad network.
- 8) Bots - Automated robots designed to carry out repetitive tasks and work like humans on the Internet. They watch ads, watch videos, fake viewing features, and deliberately or involuntarily press ads.
- 9) Click Farm - A structure of ad fraud in which massive groups of human workers (in one or greater locations) are paid for viewing and/or clicking on commercials on behalf of a third party profiting economically from fraudulent clicks
- 10) Demand Side Platform(DSP) - A platform that enables advertisers or different agencies to manage and bid multiple exchange accounts across those accounts.
- 11) Human Impression (or Valid clicks) - A click or ad legitimately interacted with a real human.
- 12) Impression - It's the primary monetary unit of online ads, usually recorded through ad servers for billing advertisers or their agencies.
- 13) Invalid Impressions (or Fraud clicks) - An impression legitimately not served to a actual human.

- 14) IP, IP Address -An unique and special numerical address that refers to an Internet related machine or set of devices.
- 15) Publisher - The website service provider, the producer or content curator for advertising websites.
- 16) Server Side Platform(SSP) - A framework used to handle the production and distribution of ad inventories to and from advertisers

There are various types of ad fraud: click fraud, impression fraud, incentivized fraud, etc. And they define every type of advertising fraud with different schemes. These include pixel stuffing, click farms, piling ads, domain spoofing, and more. But all of them contribute to the same notion. Deploy bots or fraudsters and exhaust your advertising resources somewhere in your online advertising quest. Today, a typical advertising fraud scenario works by automating the task of setting up traffic that is configured to create false metrics, and run it over a botnet on bots. These bots try to act as a human so as not to be identified as a bot and classified as blocked by ad networks. Such bots are not usually simple scripts though. These are typically full browser environments which are either handled from outside (e.g. by sending mouse / keyboard events to the browser or embedding APIs) or even manipulating an open source browser! It lets the bot perform on-page actions like adding items to a shopping cart or clicking an ad, etc.[2].

- *Online advertising*

Over the last two decades, marketing efforts have revolutionized because of the internet. Digital advertising has radically affected the way businesses serve their consumers. In fact, online advertising is so successful it has become the primary marketing method and more traditional approaches to advertising are beginning to disappear. Online advertising creates perverse incentives to target more customers, is less costly than traditional advertising and also helps the company to concentrate on key demographics[3]. There are a number of different online advertisement models available. For instance, advertisers may pay for their ads appearing as part of Google's search results. Advertisers may also publish advertisements on social media sites such as Facebook and Twitter, targeting users with similar interests in social media.

Fig. 1. Online Advertising

These advertisements come from multiple outlets, as shown in Fig 1 when a user views several advertisements on a website or app. The highlighted path represents the shortest route with

the fewest hops between the advertiser and the user. In this figure the advertiser represents the source of money for promoting its product or service, while the user serves as the initiator of activities within the publisher's website or the developers of the mobile app. Advertisers and publishers are all connected together as per the ad network. Yet the advertising system isn't that simple. There are also certain entities, as seen in the many arrows showing different relationships within that model. For instance, the DSP serves to aggregate multiple advertisers, and the SSP aggregates multiple publishers. The ad exchange however is similar to the stock exchange in that it brings both buyers and sellers together. Buyers include publishers, ad networks and SSPs while sellers include advertisers, DSPs and other ad networks. A lot of routes are possible within this hybrid environment from the advertiser to the user. In general, however, money flows from advertisers to publishers through ad networks whilst the flow of information is reciprocal. Finally ad networks may offer various pricing models (e.g. CPM, CPC, and CPA) for choosing appropriate advertising for each of their advertisers and publishers. Advertisers pay in CPM Cost Per Mile or Cost Per Impression for large-scale ad displays. Advertisers either pay in CPC Cost Per Click or Pay Per Click if users click on their ads. And in CPL or CPA Cost Per Lead or Cost Per Acquisition, advertisers pay more than ad clicks, but only if a consumer is currently performing a closed sale or a particular action. Usually, online allies running ads are charged using a pay per click (PPC) system. Their advertising revenue depends as to how much traffic they can drive to the site of the advertiser[4].

- *Pay Per Click*

Pay per click on advertising and marketing is one of the famous form of online advertising that includes advertising networks, advertisers and publishers. An advertiser generates an advertisement or a reference to their web page which they choose to show on the website of the publisher. Advertising networks finds publishers of websites that are relevant to the content, so that customers are more probably to view it. Each time a user clicks on a link, the advertiser can pay a constant amount decided to the advertising network, which in turn passes a portion of the amount to the publisher[5]. Advertising pay per click is a way for companies to purchase visits to their page rather than organically receiving visits.

- *Click fraud*

Click fraud is a way to generate fake clicks in pay per click ads. This fraud can either be done manually by click farm, or it can be done by online bots and automated software[6]. Click fraud affects pay per click advertising because it creates a false price increase on search terms. The Click fraud is not only done by the competitors rather its often, for personal vendetta or political reasons, it is maliciously committed deliberately to harm another publisher or advertiser.

- *Types of click fraud*

The simplest form of click fraud is that operated from a single computer. This can be as simple as clicking on an ad over and over manually by a person. More sophisticated users can set up an automated script to do the tedious work for them. There are few types of click fraud as listed[7]:

- 1) Crowdsourcing - One method that publishers use to maximize their ad clicks without clicking on them is crowdsourcing. For instance, in addition to their sponsored links, publishers may include text that says "help this site by clicking on those ads," this results as many clicks from people with who have no real interest in the ad content. Mostly, users who click on the ads do it very innocently to support the site they enjoy and are not aware of the fact that their mere act of support leads to click fraud.
- 2) Incentivized Traffic - A site offers some rewards for visitors to click on advertisements. For example, a clothing line gives its users clicking on ads a crash code, or a gaming site that provides players level awards to click on ads. This generates a lot of ad clicks from people who don't really care about ads and just do it for the good of the in game or for getting some discounts. It differs from crowdsourcing as those who click on the advertisement are given a real incentive.
- 3) Click Farms - Incentivized traffic offers severe consequences in a "click farm" where human beings are paid money for clicking on ads for the duration of the day. The use of actual people instead of bots is viewed really useful as human beings who are part of click farm can be taught how their actions show up more "normal" and thus more possibly to avoid automatic detection. It differs from incentivized as humans are definitely paid a precise amount for being part of click farm.
- 4) Hit Inflation Attacks - Some websites use to automatically redirect traffic to ads and then return immediately to the page they clicked on. The user doesn't see the ad, or even notice anything different than a little longer load time than normal, but the ad is counted as a hit. Site visits are translated directly into ad clicks. Since, fraud clicks rely on the natural flow of web traffic, repeated clicks from a single source do not appear suspicious.
- 5) Botnets - Code driven software applications that click on advertisements to increase the number of impressions received without advertising ever being seen by real people. Bots are highly sophisticated and can run continuously and achieve a high click-rate. They are widely used in online frauds to increase profits as they are difficult to identify and they have become pretty good at imitating the actual clicks that a person would make.
- 6) Impression fraud - This occurs when a fraudulent publisher puts advertisements in transparent frames on top of each other. It tricks advertisers into believing their advertisements are being seen, even though only the ad on top is actually visible to visitors to the site. This form of click fraud is also called ad stuffing, or ad stacking.

III. TECHNIQUES FOR CLICK FRAUD DETECTION

In current research, following approaches have been studied in analysing different click frauds. There are various means for detection and prevention of click fraud, here we try

to provide a survey and broadly classify this method including traditional and recent techniques.

- *Traffic analysis*

Traffic analysis is the method of retrieving and analyzing transactions to predict information from communication patterns. In general, for advertising the transactions performed in the ad network are observed as data for traffic analysis and larger the amount of data observed or even captured and processed, the more traffic can be inferred. R. Mouawi et al. are suggesting a novel crowdsource based system known as Click Fraud Crowdsourcing (CFC), that works with both the advertisers and ad networks and protects in opposition to practicable fraudulent clicking. In this platform of advertising, advert clicks and redirects users details related to time spend on website to the internet site of the advertiser. It is capable of monitoring the client on each advertising website and at the same time gathering various ad query information analogous to different advert network, publisher and advertiser consolidations[8]. Nagaraja et al. used timing patterns to classify fraudulent activities by clicking traffic[9]. Pearce et al. used details of real ad traffic provided by an ad network to examine the activities of the famous large-scale click fraud botnet "ZeroAccess". They estimated that the loss revenue would be around 100 K a day at advertiser side by the analysis of the behavior of this botnet[10]. Cho et al. implemented an click fraud tool that automatically generates digital advert clicks when altering the device identifier to a random value with each query and displaying that out of eight six ad networks had been in fact vulnerable to this attack. They attempt to propose how advert networks might not be motivated for click fraud, on the grounds that clicking fraud solely causes loss on the part of the advertiser, while advert networks might gain from the fraudulent traffic generated through malicious bots [11]. Dave et al. proposed a novel idea in form of a model that would allow advertisers to identify possible spam clicks on their ads primarily based on some factors, such as the time spent on their websites by the user[12]. R. Stevens et al. developed a local traffic anomaly detection model with cookie and IP address features to identify fraudulent publishers when the fraction between the number of suspicious and total requests exceeds a threshold[13]. Using unsupervised anomaly detection techniques over user behavior, BimalViswanath et al. identify bad behaviors based on the Principal Component Analysis to detect click-spam in Facebook ads[14].

- *Data Mining*

Data mining is the process of finding designs in large data sets that include approaches at the intersection of machine learning, statistics and database systems. In advertising data mining provides incentive on vast amount of click data available. Vasumati et al. used a classification algorithm for data mining to classify fraudulent clicks[15]. Haider et al. suggested an ensemble-based classifier that would detect fraudulent actions in print ads[16].

- *Machine Learning*

Machine learning is a system that is able to analyze data patterns, to predict and adapt to new situations to which they are not trained or designed specifically for. It becomes better

by experience and therefore is good for fraud detection. data set from ad records management platforms in China, Jianyu et al. conducted a supervised learning classification approach to discern out the key attributes to be taken into consideration when detecting advert fraud such as IP address, cookie and user frequency agent[17]. Fallah et al. evaluated the output of their algorithm a KNN-based click fraud classification approach having an addition of a counter field to get to the bottom of the excessive memory usage associated with KNN on a self made dataset accumulated from a search engine called parsijoo and targeted on user session information, such as user search engine clicks and IP address and other relevant keywords information's [18]. Elena et al. used a public four-day dataset from TalkingData company that manages 200 million clicks. They used the LightGBM algorithm on this large dataset. Categorical values and data unbalance are compensated by the model used. Engineering features and selection helped them in step by step improve detection performance[19]. Thejas et al. built a multi-layered Neural Network with an attached autoencoder. Their approach has good accuracy and they have used the TalkingData data set for their analysis and experiments[20]. Zang et al. implemented a CS Back Propagation Neural Network (BPNN) architecture for click fraud detection and then they use Artificial Bee Colony(ABC) to optimize BPNN connection weights and feature selection synchronously. They have used the BuzzCity company provided data set for their experiments[21].

- *Honeypot*

Honeypots are one of the most effective ways of neutering click bots and exposing the networks behind them. Here's how they work. Ad servers use special ads that are not actual ads, but bluffs indistinguishable for the human user. If a bot happens upon them and takes action, the honeypot sticks with it and does its thing, exposing the bot, leading to its IP being blocked. Haddadi et al. proposed a novel click fraud detection technique in which they developed random ads to work as honeypot in this scenario, acknowledged as bluff ads, assuming a non-malicious user would by no means generally click a random advert if their content material was once no longer relevant to them[22].

- *Other Methods*

Iqbal et al. developed an anti-virus tool that detects whether click from website is fraud or not by computing HTTP requests that are not similar with human activity; for instance mouse events. Although the user's method of detection is applicable, it does not currently apply to mobile in-app advertising[23,24]. Gabryel introduced an algorithm for click fraud detection primarily on norms received from the advertiser's web sites by the use of exclusive Javascript component. These computed features try to seize end-user interaction with the website, such as the wide variety of pages visited, scrolling statistics and different client facet information to predict the authenticity of the click[25]. Almeida et al. adopted number of rules for validation like to not include getting an IP from blacklisted IPs, acceptable HTTP headers and other requirements, this were designed to mark publishers as fraudulent in an ad network[26].

(1) Observations

We find that the research in machine learning and deep learning are promising and provide with accurate solution to the problem of click fraud. And there could be potential for solutions in this domain. We need to explore further in ensemble and gradient boosting techniques as they can give a prominent and more accurate solution for click frauds.

(2) conclusions

We have considered various security vulnerabilities in the most prominent online advertising. We systematically examine the click fraud and its types. Click Fraud is already a threat to business online and has a great potential to increase your attack radius. New technologies like the Internet of Things can collaborate indirectly to that. The need to sharpen defenses against this coup is urgent. The financial losses resulting from this danger are very significant. We analyze and survey some detection techniques used presently in different solution domains. Click fraud not only disturbs the budget advertisers but also how bots are used to corrupt your valuable data. Hence its important to be aware and evolving to come up with solutions to circumvent and prevent them. Defense Strategies must be further improved.

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Review and Comparison of an Intelligent Fire Evacuation System For Enhanced Security and Safety In Multi Storey Building Using Fuzzy Logic

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Abstract — With rapid development of sociaconomy, high-rise buildings are the need of the day. Large scale multi-storey malls, metros in the city, highway tunnels and large multi storey commercial complexes are the heart of the developing country. These places usually have a capacity of hundreds of or even thousands of people. The biggest threat to the safety of this huge mass is fire. Once a fire breaks out, due to fear, hurry and chaos, serious consequence of heavy casualties is likely to take place. Surveys reveal the fact that fast and smart evacuation systems could help reducing the life loss. No such evacuation system is found implemented except the fire extinguishers in high rise buildings. The main objective of the work is to detect fire in high rise buildings and to find out safest path for evacuation and thereby reduce the life loss. The work proposes to design and implement a fuzzy logic based system. The system will detect the fire and find out the safest path for evacuation.

Keywords: Fire Evacuation System, Multistorey Building, Fuzzy Logic.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fast evacuation is a basic part of large scale incidents. The primary objective of evacuation is to direct people away from an affected region into safe environment, and to minimize the time and hazard it takes to arrive. In spite of the way that most structures

have predefined evacuation plans and techniques, the evacuation itself is particularly a powerful procedure. Deciding of the ideal evacuation course is a confused issue because of the measure of dynamic parameters included. The best route for anybody included enormously relies upon the points of interest of the episode, the genuine condition of the structure, the condition and area of the evacuees, etc. For example, standard evacuation route might be blocked by smoke or flames, and halls might be unreasonably thin for the quantity of evacuees [1].

Fire is a phenomenon ignition showed in light, fire, and heat. There are three primary components required for fire to exist, these are; oxygen, warmth and fuel. These make up what is known as the fire triangle. The extent of every one of these components decides the idea of the fire. With fire and a portion of its results being utilized in a great deal of helpful applications, for example, cooking, power generation and the manufacturing procedure, among others, it can possibly additionally cause ruin. The need to deliver a progressively dependable fire detection system without bogus cautions has prompted the appropriation of a multi-sensor approaches. Unlike to fire detection approaches depending entirely on smoke, this methodology depends on the location of multiple fire signature. Because of the adequacy and efficiency of multi sensor based fire identification frameworks, current research on fire detection is largely focused on developing better algorithms and processing techniques based on the data received from the sensors, thereby reducing false alarms [5].

Building fire is one of the most common disaster causing casualties and deaths. Fast evacuation is not possible in case of large scale fire incidents. The main task of evacuation system is to guide people go away from an affected region to safe region and also minimize the time. Whether one can exit successfully or not, depends only on type of system design. A fuzzy logic system will implement.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Researchers have applied many technologies to early high rise building fire detection, which has acquired significant relevance in the domain, is becoming an important research and development topic. In previous papers various techniques were proposed for multi-storey building fire detection such as Artificial Neural Networks, Fuzzy Logic, A* search algorithm, Path planning algorithm, dijkshtra algorithm etc. which are discussed below.

Authors have analyzed the potential of combining remote sensor systems with Dynamic Departure and Inactive Clearing. This paper presents two strategies for dynamic evacuation directing employing a remote sensor arrange: one strategy that will lead everybody to the closest exits (and powerfully alters exit signs agreeing to the current circumstance); and a method that builds advance on this strategy by too identifying congestion in corridors and is able to supply elective courses to an exit. This system usage is difficult in genuine time. The most objectives of this investigate are: 1) To describe a strategy for making an energetic clearing steering framework in buildings utilizing wireless sensor systems. 2) To compare this strategy to static departure directing. 3) To develop and test an expansion to the elements clearing calculation, taking into consideration location of hallway congestion. This framework conclude that the dynamic will lead everybody to the closest exists and Static will too distinguish the congestion [1].

Another research is based on mobile application. This project is to design a hybrid building fire evacuation system (HBFES) using mobile phone combined with Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) techniques. The system will be implemented at Tamkang University on Lanyang campus where a central fire alarm system is installed. The HBFES is integrated onto the existing central controlled alarm system consisting of several subsystems: Database in the central controlled alarm system. A mobile phone with RFID and Near Field Communication (NFC) reader. Corresponding software packages such as Viewpoint Calculator, Path planner, MobiX3D viewer, and LBS installed on the mobile phone. Active temperature RFID sensor tags on which locations and local temperature are recorded. NFC tags for indicating the escapee's position. In this paper main problem is mobile phone must be capable for intensive RFID reading especially when time is critical [2].

According to study, the paper described how dijkshtra algorithm is best method using CAN bus and PCI bus by comparing A* search algorithm, dijkshtra algorithm and Floyd's algorithm. A* algorithm points to solving the most limited distance between one point to another. Dijkstra's algorithm points to solving the shortest separate between one point to the remaining focuses. Whereas Floyd's algorithm points to understanding the shortest distance between two of all focuses within the arrange. In this way Dijkstra's algorithm is one of the finest strategies for understanding the clearing securely [3].

One of the systems is based on Geo-spatial Information Mining Approach (SPDA). Geo-spatial information mining approach (SPDA) has been utilized to plan the manufactured cleverly module of fire sensors to make strides their capacity of fire location. And a web-GIS based spatial decision back framework can give dynamic directing benefit for evacuees and crisis directors [4].

Fig. 1 Web-GIS AHP Model Structure [4]

The most advantage of this can be intelligent space is exceptionally rich approach and open stage. This framework is valuable in extraordinary circumstance and complex building spaces such as atomic control station fire. Another advantage is low cost of equipment and computer program requirement this brilliantly space can be introduced in most public buildings [4].

On the other study, author says that the paper presents the plan and improvement of a fuzzy logic based multi-sensor fire detection framework and a web-based notice framework. It gives the fire and protects benefit with a map assisted route system. As it were for registered devices. Fuzzy logic rearranges the combination of information from the numerous sensors subsequently making it simpler to examine the regularly noisy sensor information. The framework too gives the fire and protect benefit with a map assisted navigation system to assist find the scene of a fire outbreak which is very accommodating when there's poor house and road tending to system in a neighbourhood[5].

The paper presents a virtual reality (VR) framework for fire clearing training and a common client interface through Kinect for copying clients developments, e.g. strolling, running, step side way, turn and open/close a entryway, during the training. A

virtual reality framework with a movement controller. After the framework was utilized, system found that the clients will get utilized to the framework after two times plays or after 5- min play. Framework moreover followed the player's departure course to decide whether the players took the most limited route or not. The drawback is in a few cases, players did not take the most limited way. This may be since the players tended to require the same way they were most familiar with and no exit sign was obvious which the players may notice clearly when they were evacuating [7].

Another system is based on FPGA based system by utilizing pulse width modulation method in Time NET Petrinet device (Software). The proposed cleverly clearing framework comprises of 1) Fire detection and monitoring system: Recognizes the fire within the start region, and allow caution; the faculty start to clear. 2) Fire propagation Information System: Decides the course of propagation of the fire based on the temperature measured. 3) Personnel distribution information: The number of faculty interior the floor is identified by the IR sensor arranged at each door. The disadvantage of that's as it were multi entryway control and fire caution framework during an emergency condition [8].

On the other study, system is utilized particle swarm optimization strategy. Particle swarm optimization is utilized to optimize the evacuation route. Since it is simple to actualize and has exceptionally few parameters. PSO calculation is heuristic calculation. It does not continuously provide correct result whereas it points to approach to the precise result. The PSO calculation comprises of the taking after steps;

- 1) The beginning run is made with arbitrarily positions and speeds up to number of particles.
- 2) For each particle within the run, the fitness value is calculated.

- 3) The neighbourhood best (pbest) is found within the current era for all particles.
- 4) The global best (gbest) is chosen from the nearby eras of the current generation.
- 5) Positions and speeds are updated [9].

III. COMPARISON OF ALGORITHM/ TECHNIQUE

Sr. No.	Algorithm/ Technique	Outcomes of Algorithm/ Technique
1.	A* search algorithm	It detect Crowd Congestion, But time consuming algorithm.
2.	Mobile application	Mobile phone must be capable for intensive RFID reading especially when time is critical.
3.	Dijkshtra algorithm	It provides a shortest distance between one point to remaining point. It has high software expenditure. Undesirable interaction more probable.
4.	Geo spatial data mining approach	It is a highly demanding field because huge amounts of spatial data have been collected in various applications. Cost is high.
5.	3 D Training model	Limitation of capturing space of Kinect device, and user must face the screen while using the system.

6.	Particle Swarm Optimization	Optimize the evacuation route. Easy to implement. It has a low convergence rate in the iterative process.
7.	Dynamic Evacuation & Static evacuation	Dynamic will lead everyone to the nearest exists. Static will also detect the congestion. But, Real time is hard.

IV. FLOW CHART OF PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

V. CONCLUSION

For fire evacuation system many algorithm are used. Like A* search algorithm, Dijkstra algorithm, Floyd's algorithm, FPGA, Geo spatial data mining approach, Fuzzy logic, Artificial Intelligence. The comparative study says that the fuzzy logic is best suited for fast and safe fire evacuation in high rise building. This framework can work with any sort of inputs whether it is uncertain, distorted or noisy input information. The result of fuzzy logic system is in three way low fire, medium fire, and high fire. The development of Fuzzy Logic Frameworks is simple

and understandable. Fuzzy logic comes with scientific concepts of set hypothesis and the thinking of that's quite simple. It gives a very efficient arrangement to complex issues in all fields of life because it takes after human thinking and choice making. The calculations can be described with small information, so small memory is required [5]. The system can be divided into two parts: Transmitter and Receiver. In transmitter, there is number of sensors for collecting the data and from that, this data is transmitted to the receiver using NodeMCU Micro-controller by Wi-Fi. In receiver, there is a one Wi-Fi module (NodeMCU) which will receive the data from transmitter side. GSM modem, LED strips and speakers are connected to the NodeMCU at receiver side. The system can also provide the direction for evacuation through light strips and speakers. The SMS using a Global System for Mobile Communication (GSM) module will be sent to fire brigade and police station.

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Design of A Real Time Anti-spoofing Mechanism In Face Recognition For Security And Reliability Based on Image Processing Using OpenCV

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Abstract— At the present time, securing facerecognition systems against spoofing attacks have been recognized as a real challenge. Spoofing attacks are conducted by printing or displaying a digital picture or video in front of sensor. In order to make better quality of face recognition system in virtual environment, an antispoofing mechanism using OpenCV is proposed. The main aim of this proposed system is to detect real or fake face, liveness detection through video and for this design and develop an efficient algorithm. This project/paper describes a hardware implementation of anti-Spoofing Detection system using raspberry pi. The system is programmed using python and OpenCV. In this system camera will capture the image of face. Then extract the feature of that image using OpenCV. After that extracted image will matched with stored image. If image will match, relay module will on. If not, shows that ‘image is fake’ on display (PC).

Keywords: Raspberry Pi, Face LivenessDetection, Face Spoofing, Face Detection

I. INTRODUCTION

In face recognition system imposter can obtain legal identity authentication by presenting the printed images, downloaded images or candid videos to the sensor. In this system design and develop an efficient algorithm for face spoofing mechanism. Among variously methods for solving the problem

of face liveness detection, the current face-live detection methods can be divided into the following three categories. 1] Photo Attack, 2] Mask Attack, 3] Video Attack.

Fig. 1 a) Print photo attack; b) 3D mask attack; c) Replay attack (Photo/Video)

The face is the most common biometric parameter which has been used in personal and commercial applications such as access to Laptop, personal computers, ATM machines (Automated Teller Machines), online banking, airports, and border control etc [1]. These kinds of attacks are mostly common due to the easy availability of the photo or video of a person from the social networking websites such as Flickr, Facebook and Instagram. Majority of the existing face recognition methodologies are not designed to differentiate live from fake faces thus creating a major security issue. Hence, it needs an additional secure layer of face spoofing (or liveness) detection [5].

Spoofing causes distortion in the image quality. Analysing the distortion and also the image quality is one of the techniques used to identify whether the face is genuine or spoof [4]. The goal of face spoofing detection is to recognize whether the tested face has a place to a live or a fake source. It has been

found that a certain kind of textural pattern will be presented when using a fake face photo or video. Subsequently, a well-known branch of existing work misuses this assumption by recognizing the textural pattern contrasts between the genuine and spoofed face [5].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Face recognition systems have been extensively used in government as well as commercial applications such as mobile, banking and surveillance systems etc. In the last 10 years, the whole biometric community such as researchers, developers, and retailers has worked on challenging tasks to develop a more accurate protection method against spoofing threats. The goal of this paper is to provide a detailed study of antispoofing methodologies.

Authors have analysed an enhanced face local binary feature (ELBP) of a face map is extracted as a classification feature to identify whether the face map is a real face or a fake face. The facial pictures acquired by printing the photographs are typically particularly like those got from the living faces. Therefore, it is important to choose an appropriate feature space that can recognize two kinds of pictures (liveness or mocking facial pictures). To get such a feature space, we become familiar with the unpretentious contrasts between genuine face pictures and printed facial pictures. Then, as a result, a feature space that emphasizes the differences is devised. The features feeded to the classifier are combined by 59 enhanced characters which is encoded from the image via ELBP. Then the problem of face liveness detection can be solving via one image. Relative investigation shows that ELBP is better than LTP and other propelled face liveness discovery strategies for facial example examination [1].

Another author goal is to build a tool that can distinguish video replay assault in indoor situations with complex foundation and lighting conditions from indoor and outside. We likewise attempted to improve the exactness by (a) implementing a model for segmentation process between the object/user and background area, so that the model is not only covered the face area, but also all parts of the object's/user's body and (b) using only motion analysis. The motion to be analyzed is defined as changes of spatial features between frames, not only on specific features such as eye blink, mouth movement, and so forth. The proposed method consists of two steps. The first one is object/segmentation to separate the regions between the object and background area and the second one is classification. Segmentation was done by locating the object area using a model. That is why, as a pre-processing step, building a human body model should be performed. This study proposed an approach for detecting video-based face spoofing by motion analysis, with model-based segmentation. This work still used the background in indoor with static conditions. It did not include the background in outdoor with dynamic conditions. Therefore, the future study needs to be able to detect face spoofing with dynamic background conditions including if shadow appears. For the segmentation process was also expected to be performed automatically [2].

By further study, work presents a novel and engaging approach for identifying confront spoofing utilizing colour texture analysis. We misuse the joint colour texture data from the luminance and the chrominance channels by extricating complementary low-level include depictions from distinctive colour spaces. More specifically, the feature histograms are computed over each image band separately. To begin with, the face is identified, edited and standardized into an $M \times N$ pixel image. At that point, holistic surface descriptions are extricated from each

colour channel and the coming about feature vectors are concatenated into an improved feature vector in order to induce an overall representation of the facial colour surface. The ultimate feature vector is fed to a binary classifier and the yield score value depicts whether there's a live individual or a fake one in front of the camera. The facial representations extracted from distinctive colour spaces utilizing distinctive texture descriptors can moreover be concatenated in order to advantage from their complementary [3].

Another proposed system based on Image Distortion Analysis (IDA) and Image Quality Assessment (IQA). In image distortion analysis, extracts the features that capture the facial subtle elements. It extracts four diverse highlights (specular reflection, blurriness, chromatic moment, and colour diversity) to create the IDA (Image Distortion Analysis) include vector. The existing strategies in image quality assessment, extracts several general image qualities highlights to make IQA (Image Quality Assessment) include vector. The designed framework utilizes a hybrid scheme of both IDA and IQA. In expansion, it moreover extracts the Fourier based and Wavelet based features of the image. A Neural Network (NN) classifier is utilized for the training. Fig 2 shows the generalized block diagram of the system [4].

Fig. 2 Generalized block diagram of the designed system

One of the system presents a novel feature, namely, SBP-TOP, to effectively identify such spoofing. SBP-TOP presents the texture information for the face region from both spatial and temporal perspectives. Given the face video, the framework will to begin with prepare it in an appropriate form so that the afterward SBPTOP include might be extracted easily. Finally, a few classic classifiers will be utilized to predict its genuineness. The rule behind SBP is that, it explores the higher arrange of the image (picture moments) instead of the image itself so that the descriptor will be more strong to picture noises. SBP-TOP has two properties. Firstly, it can represent the facial characteristics in a more noise-resistant adaptation than the well-known LBP. Secondly, the visual characteristics along video's time dimension are coordinates to its unique form [5].

Author introduce a face spoofing detection based on color distortion analysis, which captures the chromatic aberration from a face image. Color distortion analysis extracts color moment and positioned histogram features, which create 116 highlight vector. The include vector at that point sent to Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to perform dimensionality reduction. For classifying a live or spoof face picture, a Naïve Bayes classifier performed on the principal components gotten from PCA. The proposed framework comprises of 4 stages: (1) normalization of input face image, (2) feature extraction utilizing color moment and ranked histogram, (3) dimensionality reduction, and (4) classification [6].

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

At the present time, securing face recognition frameworks against spoofing attacks have been recognized as a genuine challenge. Spoofing attacks are conducted by printing or showing a computerized picture or video before sensor. In

order to form way better quality of face recognition framework in virtual environment, an antispoofing mechanism using openCV is proposed. The main idea of the proposed approach is shown as block diagram in fig 3.

Fig. 3 Block diagram of proposed method

The most point of this proposed framework is to distinguish genuine or fake face, liveness detection through video and for this plan and create a proficient algorithm. This paper depicts an equipment execution of anti-Spoofing Detection framework utilizing raspberry pi. The framework is modified utilizing python and openCV. In this framework camera will capture the picture of face and deliver to the Raspberry pi board. At that point extract the feature of that image utilizing openCV. After that extracted picture will coordinated with stored picture. In case picture will match, relay module will on. On the off chance that not, shows that “image is fake” in show (PC). An example where this technology is used is in airport security systems. In order to recognize a face, the camera software must first detect it and identify the features before making identification. Face detection uses classifiers, which are algorithms that recognize what is either a face or not a face in an picture. Classifiers have been prepared to identify faces utilizing

thousands to millions of pictures in arrange to urge more precision.

IV. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

Haar Cascade is a machine learning object detection algorithm used to identify objects in an image or video and based on the concept of features. It is a machine learning based approach where a cascade function is trained from a lot of positive and negative images. It is then used to detect objects in other images. The algorithm has four stages: 1) Haar Feature Selection 2) Creating Integral Images 3) Adaboost Training 4) Cascading Classifiers. It is well known for being able to detect faces and body parts in an image, but can be trained to identify almost any object. Haar cascade employments “integral image” concepts to compute the “features” identified. Haar Cascades utilize the Ada-boost learning calculation which chooses a little number of critical highlights from a huge set to provide an effective result of classifiers at that point utilize cascading strategies to identify face in a picture. Haar cascade classifier is based on Viola Jones detection algorithm which is prepared in given a few input faces and non-faces and training a classifier which recognizes a face.

V. CONCLUSION

For face spoofing detection system many methods are used i.e. local binary pattern, color texture analysis, motion analysis, IDA & IQA, stastical binary pattern etc. Proposed method used openCV which open source programming library. In this framework presented various frauds in face recognition based biometric system. the proposed framework will conclude that it is utilized for an actuate face liveness detection through video stream and for detection of genuine face and fake face for reliability and security utilizing opencv and effective algorithm.

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A Survey on Vision-Based Real-Time System for Indian Sign Language Recognition

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Abstract—Sign language is widely used by deaf and dumb people to communicate. A sign language is formed by different handshapes, movements, and orientations of hands or body, or facial expressions. Normal people find difficulty in understanding these sign languages. This creates a communication gap between them. By creating an artificial sign language recognition system, we can reduce this communication gap. Very little work has been done in recognition of Indian sign language because of the lack of standardization and complexity of gestures. Recently, researchers from India have started working on ISL to develop automatic Indian sign language recognition systems. Mainly three steps are involved in sign language recognition—preprocessing, feature extraction and classification

Keywords— Sign Language Recognition, Hand Gesture, Indian Sign Language, translation, Feature Extraction, Edge Detection.

II. INTRODUCTION

Sign language is widely used by people with speaking disabilities. It has completely different vocabulary from spoken and written languages. It uses combinations of hand shapes, movement, position, palm orientation, arms or body, and facial expressions to convey meaning. But, Sign languages are not international. Every country has its unique sign language developed with a number of grammatical differences. Figure 1 shows the sign language representation of ISL alphabets. As per the survey done by the Indian government in the year 2011, over 2.68 crores of people in India suffer from disabilities. Out of this 18.9% people have speech and 7.5% people have a hearing disability [7]. Normal people do not understand sign languages. So, they find difficult to communicate with deaf people. So, there is a requirement of a system that can recognize sign language symbols and translate it in corresponding text or sound. This will help to reduce the

communication gap and eliminate the help of a sign language interpreter.

Sign language recognition is a crucial area of research because there are many challenges in the development of such systems. Mainly, two approaches are used for this purpose: Hardware-based and Vision-based [1]. In the hardware-based method, the user needs to use special wearable devices that contain the weight of cables and sensors. Such kind of method reduces the naturalness of communication and it may also turn out to be expensive. Where the vision-based method uses Image processing [2] and Computer Vision [3] techniques that need a

camera and software for processing image gestures. It works in two-step: sign capturing and sign analysis. Because of reduced complexity to the user, it is a widely used approach.

Fig.1. ISL Signs for Alphabets

As there are lots of difficulties in developing a sign recognition system, this is a valuable research area. Most researchers concentrate on American Sign Language (ASL) since most gestures in American Sign Language are single hand and fewer complexes. Another benefit in ASL is that it has standard database available to use. When compared to ASL, ISL

(Indian Sign Language) has both hands and complex gestures. And ISL has no standard database available. So a very small amount of research work has been done in this area. Recently, more researchers have started researching in this area. In this paper, we have discussed widely used techniques in sign language recognition system.

III. RECOGNITION SYSTEM

In Most of the Recognition systems, some general steps are used for process. Which contains Image preprocessing, feature extraction, and image classification is used. There are 2 parts of the process: Training and Testing.

Here is a graphical representation of simple sign

language recognition system is shown in Figure 2.

Fig.2. Signs Language Recognition system

During the training phase, a dataset is used to train the classifier. For this, own database is created or available database may be used. Firstly training images should be captured. To train the system, these images will be represented with class tables. Important steps of this phase include dataset creation, preprocessing, feature extraction, and classifier training. Once the system is trained, the testing phase will start. In the testing phase, images with unknown classes will appear. The testing phase will use same steps as training phase to classify images. Different techniques are used in different stages of recognition.

IV. SURVEY OF EXISTING METHODS

A. Pre-processing

Once the image is captured, segmentation techniques are used to detect skin and track it. Then used many techniques to reduce unnecessary noise from an image. In pre-processing step, a

region of interest (ROI) is generated. ROI can be hands for hand gesture centered system or both hands and face if facial expression also included. For this process, skin color detection is used. Many color spaces available for this process.

RGB model is a color-camera generated format that contains information about the amount of Red, Green, and Blue color in pixel. A remarkable property of this model is the matte surface^[4]. These values can detect similar colored pixels. Therefore, we can use these values to detect skin-colored pixels and use it for further process.

YCbCr model is an encoded non-linear RGB color model. This model is generally used in the digital world. Because this model makes it easier to discard some redundant color information. In this color model, luminance value is stored as (Y), and chrominance value is stored as (Cb and Cr)^[4].

HSV model is more about how people see color rather than RGB color model. Hue (H) stands for angle in color hexagon where corresponding colors vary from red, through yellow, green, cyan, blues, and magenta, black to red. Saturation (S) varies from 0.0 to 1.0, from unsaturated to fully saturated. Value (V) varies from 0.0 to 1.0, indicates brightness of color^[4]. RGB has values like (15,236,57), whereas for HSV it will be (45°, v1/4, 0.45).

B. Feature Extraction

Feature extraction is used for extracting useful components of image for the description of an image. The output of this process is a vector representation of image features which is used in classifier. The accuracy of a system is majorly dependent upon this step. Therefore we have to choose this method very carefully.

- 1) *Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG)*: Histogram of Oriented Gradients^[5], originally proposed by Dalal and Triggs, is commonly used descriptor for the description of an object's shape or color. HOG is used as a descriptor in the system^[5]. First, it divides the image into smaller cells and generates a single-dimensional histogram of a pixel in each cell. By normalization in these local histograms, we can achieve invariance in illumination.
- 2) *Histogram of Contour Detection (HCD)*: HCD^[6] is used to calculate the contour of the object. First, it calculates the pixel values of the image. If a major difference occurs between pixel values parallel it will consider as a contour. It also divides the image into smaller cells and generates histogram of contour direction in each cell.

- 3) *Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT)*: SIFT^[8] is an advanced feature descriptor of HOG. First, the Difference of Gaussian (DoG) filters are applied to the image. Second, local maxima and minima key points represented in scale-space. Then, poorly defined points will be reduced. For every point, a histogram is generated of gradient orientation. As gradient is dependent upon local maxima or minima, it is rotation invariant.
- 4) *Principal Component Analysis (PCA)*: Principal Component Analysis^[9], uses Eigenvectors and Eigen values like features to describe an image. First, all the training images are stored in 2D vectors. Second, mean image is generated and eliminated from this vector space. A covariance matrix is generated from the resultant space. To reduce the data dimension, the first few principal eigenvectors as feature vectors.

Table.1. Feature Extraction Techniques

Methods	Advantages	Disadvantages
Histogram of Oriented Gradients	Provides global information in larger division and local details in smaller divisions	High memory requirement, Not invariant
Histogram of Contour Detection	Works on edges that reduces number of features	Not invariant, Color independent
Scale Invariant Feature Transform	Accuracy, Scale and Rotation invariant,	Complex, Higher computational time
Principle Component Analysis	Low memory requirements, Immune to noise	Not invariant

C. Classification

After feature extraction, a classifier is used for classification of signs in different classes. Vectors received from the feature extraction method generated from training images used to create classes. In testing phase, classifiers use these classes to recognize signs in images. Here is a list of mostly used classifiers in image processing.

Hidden Markov Model (HMM): A Hidden Markov Model is a classifier that has a finite number of classes and it has in-between connection of states indicates transactions. Each state

is described with transaction probability and output probability that defines condition probability of selecting each output symbols.

Artificial Neural Network (ANN): ANN is another widely used classifier working based on the human brain. This network has one input layer, one output layer and some hidden layers. A supervised technique is used for the training purpose of ANN classifier. Inputs are given through neurons to the system and the output is obtained from neurons from output layer.

1) *Support Vector Machine (SVM)*: SVM is used as a supervised classifier. It trains the system with pre-classified data and creates boundaries among all classes. Then whenever a new object appears, it projects that object and in whichever class it appears, SVM will classify that object in that class.

2) *K Nearest Neighbor (KNN)*: KNN is a classifier that works with the nearest training dataset. KNN takes training dataset and put it on a graph with predefined classes. When a new object appears, whichever class's object is nearest to that object, the classifier will classify that new object with that object's class.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an analysis of different methods for sign language recognition techniques. It showed the need for an automatic sign language detection system. And it also showed difficulties for developing such kind of system. The researchers should focus on developing such a system that can detect hand signs and face in complex background. It observed that single features may not provide satisfactory results and performance. Therefore, combining multiple features rightly may provide better results.

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Lip Movement Recognition and Speech Conversion using Image Processing for Impaired People in Gujarati Language

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Abstract—The lip reading system is very helpful system especially for deaf and dumb people. People are lucky to make communication with each other by a voice but unfortunately, few of them are not able to communicate using voice. An extensive work have be done in different language but unfortunately, that cannot done in the Gujarati language. There are many techniques available to communicate with impaired or special people. This paper aims to communicate between normal and deaf – dumb people in Gujarati and English language. In the proposed system, video will be separated into number of the frames. Then face is detected using separated frame by applying Viola-Jones algorithm. After the face detection, lip extracted from the frame. After that, extracted lip frame will be used to detect lip movement by applying ANN algorithm. Generated result of ANN algorithm will detect word and it will get convert into text. Finally, the generated word will announced by speaker.

Keywords—lip reading, viola- jones algorithm, ANN algorithm, lip movement, Generate word, speaker.

I. INTRODUCTION

As human, we are blessed by ‘Speech’ as God’s gift. Speech is the main tool forhuman communication but many people in the world are suffering from some disordersome are suffering from throat infection or throat cancer and they are not able to speak. In some accidental cases when a

person is hospitalized or has multiple organs paralysis/fractures and not able to speak or move his hands, they cannot communicate with other people. Unfortunately, some people are unable to communicate with normal people due to some problem. This system is to help them such a way that their lip gestures are recognized and voice commands are generated accordingly to lip movement. Proposed system is for abnormal people so they communicate easily. In proposed system, capture a video by a camera. That save video converted into number of the frame. In this frame detect a face and lip area. Using the Viola-Jones algorithm. The ANN algorithm used forlipmovement detection. The proposed system detect the word in English and Gujarati language. That detected word shown in the text and convert into speech.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In [1] this paper, discuss about the different types of lip detection, lip feature extraction and databases.

A. Types of Lip detection

B. Types of Lip feature extraction

C. Types of Data Bases

In [2] this paper, lip movement recognition for Myanmar consonants. Lip-reading Moore neighborhood and for the classification are used. In this paper, only one and two syllable consonants are recognized. Lip feature tracking robust algorithm are used. Lip localization is focus or important part of this paper. In lip localization part, divide a ROI and background using the decorrelation stretching color enhancing and CIEL*a*b color transformation method are used. Skin and background colors are it then not easily separated ROI so for that kalman filter is use to eliminate a noise and unwanted information in image. OSTu thresholding is also known as adaptive threshold.

In [3] this paper, proposed system divided into 3 parts:

- Input a video, that video convert into number of frames and detect the mouth region.
- Crop the lip and encoding the feature from the input sequence of image.
- Cascaded attention- CTC decoder generate text from encoded features.

In this paper for end-to-end lip reading cascaded attention- CTC deep learning model. LCA Net network used. Here, LCA Net use for the encoding the video frame. 3D convolution high network and bi-directional GRU layers that effectively capture both short-term and long-term spatiotemporal information. ASMS or AAMS model is use for feature extraction in machine lip

reading. In encoding part, RBMs and temporal dynamics model is use for pre training. These two models by an LSTM. Mixing of this two models through a bi-directional LSTM recognize a video and audio features. This is 'EESSEN' framework based method.

In [4] this paper, recorded video detect a lip movement local binary pattern (LBP) operator use for the feature extraction. Two methods for silent speech interface.

- Electromagnetic device for tracking tongue and lip movement
- Ultrasound and optical camera to detect tongue and lip movements.

It is invariance against monotonic gray level changes is main property of LBP operator. KNN classifier is use because it is fundamental and simple classification method. In this system, "WATER" word are recognize, all algorithm are design in MATLAB software.

In [5] this paper, Viola-Jones algorithm use for face and mouth region detection. The Colour space conversion and clustering method results in separation of lip from non-lip pixel. Which are further subjected to morphological operation and ellipse fitting for an efficient lip contour extraction. For lip segmentation jumping snake method and vidTimit database are used. In the proposed system 43 people video, audio recording and testing. Lip contour extraction method divided into 3 main blocks.

- Preprocessing of input image. In this block, video divided into frames.
- Detect mouth and face using the HSV Colour space method.
- In post processing that detect mouth and face generate accordingly output or extract a feature.

In [6] this paper is based on the survey taken for the lip reading techniques. Feature extraction & classification are the keynotes for this paper. A video will be converted into number of frames, and that frames will be extracted features effectively, and will get the information related to the motion of various aspects. Feature extractions can be classified as follows:

A. Geometrical features

In geometrical features, we can get the information about various parameters like height, width, area, visible regions, ratio of height and width and many more.

B. Image-based features

Transforms can be used for Image-Based Features. There are many transforms can be used for the specific methods, some of them are as, Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT), Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) and Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) used. Among these various transforms, "Discrete Cosine Transform" is most popular.

C. Model-based features

Model based features can be used for locating and tracking predetermined points in an image. Hence, it can be very helpful in extracting features. Constrained Local Model (CLM) and Sample Active Contour Model (SACM) can be used in model-based features.

D. Motion based features

If the object in process or moving or not in a stable manner, then motion based feature will be used to extract the features. Whereas, AAM model are used for the head motion.

Classification: Information will be extracted into number of frames, and that frames will fed to classifier for the classification. HMM, FSM (Finite State Machine) and SVM (Support Vector Machine) etc. used in the same process.

In [7] this paper listeners decode the information, inferring the verbal and nonverbal cues conveyed by the speaker. This process must considered to create more believable facial movements for conversational agents (CAs). The essential relationship between speech articulation and emotional expressed content is directly exploited in the model by performing multitask learning (MTL). Said secondary tasks are relevant to variations in the orofacial movements. Emotion modulation is different under different phonetic units like, pronouncing /b/ and /a/ with a smile. Motion capture recordings of an actor will be used

in while speaking, finding the weights associated with each canonical shape during different diphones, and triphones. They used motion capture recordings of an actor while speaking, which finds the weights associated with each canonical shape during different diphones, and triphones. The second approach uses generative models to implicitly model speech coarticulation. Choi et al. proposed to use hidden Markov models (HMM) inversion to predict lip movements from speech. Speech and visual features are jointly modeled for each phoneme with three state HMMs. Objective and subjective evaluations showed better results for their approach compared with an HMM-based approach. The IEMOCAP corpus includes audio, video, and motion capture recordings of dyadic interactions between ten actors. Therefore, this study only considers the recordings from the first female subject (418 speaking turns), where the distribution of emotions is 66 (neutral), 72 (anger), 57 (happiness), 42 (sadness), 0 (disgust), 3 (fear), 68 (frustrated), 4 (surprised), and 0 (other). There are 106 sentences without consensus label. For emotional features, we use the extended Geneva minimalistic acoustic parameter set (eGeMAPS), which was carefully selected as a reduced set for paralinguistic problems. This feature set comprises 88 statistics extracted over 23 low-level descriptors (LLDs). We propose two multitask learning structures to integrate the spectral and eGeMAPS features, where our goal is to learn the best shared representation that optimizes the prediction of facial movements.

III. PROPOSED METHOD OF SYSTEM

In proposed system, take a video via webcam and save into pc or save video convert into number of frames. In general, video is a sequence of frames. The average framing of video based on

length of the video. In that image using the Viola-Jones algorithm, detect a face and ROI. In this system, ROI is a lip so detect a lip area and show in boundary box. If change the threshold then detect the different part of face. After that detect part extracted using a Viola-Jones algorithm. Get the major axis length; minor axis length and other feature are extract. Apply the ANN algorithm for the classification of system. Based on entropy and matching with dataset of image generate a word or text. That word display in command window. Word convert into speech and announced by speaker. In proposed system "Hello", "KemChho" and "OM" word generated.

IV. FLOWCHART OF SYSTEM

V. HARDWARE

Camera and speaker is hardware of proposed system.

- Camera used for the capturing a video. In proposed system laptop internal camera are used.
- Speaker used for announced a word.

D.

VI. RESULTS

A. Detecting an "OM" word in image:

Subject	No. of attempts to derived results	No. of successful attempts	Accuracy (%)
Nisha	50	40	80
Maulika	50	42	84
Riddhi	50	39	78
Mahin	50	44	88
Farhan	50	38	76

B. Detecting an "OM" word in video:

Subject	No. of attempts to derived results	No. of successful attempts	Accuracy (%)
Nisha	50	42	84
Maulika	50	40	80
Riddhi	50	44	88
Mahin	50	41	82
Farhan	50	39	78

C. Detecting a "KemChho" word:

Subject	No. of attempts to derived results	No. of successful attempts	Accuracy (%)
Nisha	50	45	90
Maulika	50	40	80
Riddhi	50	42	84
Mahin	50	43	86
Farhan	50	40	80

VII. CONCLUSION

This system for impaired or deaf and dumb people. It is for communication purpose. It required a webcam and MATLAB software. In a proposed system, capture a video by a webcam. That video and save video convert into number of frames. Detect and segmented, face and lip area. Then after use an ANN algorithm for a classification. Detect a word based on classification, property and database. That word convert into speech.

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Meteorological Big Data mining: A survey

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Abstract — Meteorological data is generated on day to day basis through various techniques. Hadoop distributed file system is used to handle such a rapid growth of data by storing data in distributed system. There are many architecture exist which uses Hive and pig query tools to extract data from HDFS and then apply Mapreduce for analyzing data. Apache spark is also used for faster analysis. To further improve time efficiency for large datasets, data mining algorithms are also used in distributed manner. All work has been done on traditional framework with the lack of any user interface and effective visualization. We will propose a framework which is more efficient to handle meteorological data with user interface and effective visualization.

Keywords— Meteorological data, big data, data mining.

I. INTRODUCTION

Meteorological data comes under the big data as it is sharing the same characteristics of big data. Meteorological data is growing rapidly. Meteorological data is large volume of data which is generating at rapid rate. In addition the meteorological data is unstructured data with inconsistencies and uncertainty. To store, access and handle these much amount of data is a crucial task [1].

There are different tools and techniques available for handling large volumes of meteorological data. **Hadoop** is core of most technologies. Hadoop provides the best

framework for storing unstructured data in a distributed manner. It also provides fault tolerance and high throughput for accessing the data. **Hive** is the data warehouse tool, built on Hadoop platform. It is query language through which user can query the data. **Apache spark** is used to perform some analysis on the data faster than mapreduce. It also provides support for multiple languages like java, Scala and python. It also supports SQL queries, machine learning, streaming and graph algorithms. **HBase** is column oriented NoSQL database which is used to store data in table format and we can use hive, pig query tools to extract data from it. **Cassandra** is also column oriented NoSQL database which provides flexible data storage. It is used where write is major operations as it performs write operations faster.

The meteorological data is unstructured data which is in raw format so we have to transform it into usable format. Data cleaning is performed to handle missing values and noisy data. Data transformation is also applied on the data by normalizing and deriving new attributes in data.

Different data mining techniques can be applied on the meteorological data. If the dataset is labelled then to classify the day as rainy, foggy and sunny supervised algorithms like Decision tree, random forest, Naive Bayes and support vector machine classification algorithms can be used. To predict the rainfall in future, regression can also be applied on the data. K means is applied on unlabeled data to find the clusters based on similarity of data point values. Anomaly detection algorithms are also applied

to detect abnormal events like flood, storm and many more.

REVIEW OF VARIOUS BIG DATA MINING APPROACHES

6) The Establishment and data mining of meteorological data warehouse.

In this paper [2], the authors have proposed warehouse system for handling increasing growth of meteorological data. The design of warehouse system is based on Hadoop distributed file system. The proposed system is basically master slave based architecture with three layers as shown in below Figure 1.

Figure 1. The framework of Meteorological data warehouse file system

In storage layer Hadoop distributed file system is used for storing large amount of meteorological data into distributed manner. Hadoop contains Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) which provides fault tolerance and high throughput compare to normal file system. HBase is used for storing the unstructured data into some tabular format for easily querying and analyzing data in future use. Map reduce is used for performing some computation on the data. Hive is used to generate map reduce tasks for analyzing metadata of meteorological data which is stored under HBase. In User layer data management is done through terminal and

meteorological application services. In master management layer system configuration, namespace maintenance and operational management is done. The framework is tested by applying other datasets such as PokerHand, Adult, Wilt, Yeast, Balance scale and wine by considering all attributes of the datasets. Map reduce is applied on these datasets which gives output in key value form. As these datasets falls under classification category of data mining, Improved Naive Bayes algorithm is applied on the resultant data from mapreduce task and testing is performed on different dataset. Performance evaluation is done by comparing accuracy and timing of testing dataset for proposed system and traditional system. As Table 1 and Table 2 shows for all datasets, testing time is reduced and accuracy rate is increased because of storing and processing data in a distributed manner.

The table of using the improved naive bayes algorithm

Data set	Training time (s)	Testing time (s)	Accuracy rate (%)
PokerHand	28	662	92.4006
Adult	4	14	82.1560
Wilt	3	2	78.9553
Yeast	2	1	42.0866
Balance Scale	2	1	72.5642
Wine	2	1	90.3964

Table 1. Improved Naive Bayes Algorithm

The table of using the traditional naive bayes algorithm

Data set	Test time (s)	Accuracy rate (%)
PokerHand	954	91.7877
Adult	17	79.3333
Wilt	4	75.8975
Yeast	1	42.1976
Balance Scale	1	72.5642
Wine	1	91.0569

Table 2. Traditional Naive Bayes Algorithm

In future, the authors can compare the performance of other classification algorithms such as Decision tree, Random Forest and Support vector machine with respect to Naïve Bayes.

B. Supervised classification of rainfall coverage data in Andhra Pradesh using support vector machine.

In this paper [3], the authors have used Meteorological data which is in the form of TIFF. Tiff format comes under the raster type of data. Raster images are collection of pixels which are represented in matrix form. The rainfall dataset is preprocessed and then data of Andhra Pradesh region is extracted from the whole dataset. For training purpose some samples are extracted from the selected data. After training phase SVM model is applied on the data. In testing phase, model is validated by giving unknown data as input to that model and find accuracy of the model. In testing phase input data should not be the part of selected training samples of Andhra Pradesh region. The performance evaluation is done using confusion matrix and error matrix which represents how many values are correctly classified or not. Regions of Andhra Pradesh map is classified as Excess if rainfall coverage is greater than 20%, Normal if rainfall coverage is -19% to +19% and deficient if rainfall coverage is -20% to -59%. The confusion matrix shows that all values are categorized correctly and model achieved 100% accuracy for classification based on district map of Andhra Pradesh.

The authors have not mentioned the data size. In future, the authors should also consider variation of rainfall coverage inside every districts.

[5] SMASH: A Cloud-Based Architecture for Big Data Processing and Visualization of Traffic Data

In this paper [4], the authors have proposed one software stack named by SMASH which contains components like Hadoop distributed File System (HDFS), Spark, Apache Geomesaaccumulo and Geoserver. The authors have used cloud facility provided by Australia under the NeCTAR project. To handle large amount of data the authors have created range of virtual machines with some quite good specifications like 4GB core and 30 GB storage to Highly efficient machines with 16GB cores and 480 GB

storage in which storage can be extended to 100 petabyte also. The data is collected from the transport department of Sydney Coordinated adaptive Traffic system. Traffic data is spatio temporal data in nature. Geomesa is used for indexing of spatio temporal data, and Geoserver is used for visualization of data with maps. Testing of The SMASH architecture performed using Adelaide and Victoria dataset which contains 181 million records from 2008 to 2014 year. Distributed environment is created using 4 Machines with 4-core, 30GB disk and 12GB RAM specifications. SMASH is capable of processing 15GB dataset without exhausting resources. As compare to traditional Hadoop map reduce system, SMASH performs better by providing better big analytic platform. Use of Accumulo and Geomesa in platform makes it more suitable for handling spatiotemporal data efficiently. Additionally, spark is used rather than hadoopmapreduce which performs better for processing large data.

In future, the authors can give users flexibility to select areas of interest and perform analyses of it and at the end visualize it in a more effective way.

[13] A novel clustering of big data in hadoop ecosystem

In this paper [5], the authors have proposed hybrid clustering on big data. To handle big data Hadoop has been used. The data is collected from National Climatic data center (NCDC) from 1901 year, the dataset contains hourly data from 20000 stations from full globe. The K means and Hierarchical clustering are used for hybrid approach. In the hybrid approach, K means is applied on a dataset and mapper class will map the data point with the centroid of the cluster in which the data point belongs. After K means Hierarchical algorithm is applied on the remaining data points. Hashmap is applied to remove redundancy from the clusters formed by both the algorithms. Input of the Mapper class is weather file for specific year. Mapper is applied on both the algorithm and output of mapper class is given as input to the reducer class. Output of Mapper class is a key value pair here key is date and value is temperature. Output of

reducer is aggregated value for unique key. Reducer will merge the cluster of both algorithms. Precision, Recall and F1 score is used for performance evaluation of the algorithms. Hybrid clustering have 99% precision, 82 % Recall and 90% F1 score.

Hybrid clustering is taking more time to execute than kmeans and hierarchical clustering methods, Different parameters needed to reduce execution time of hybrid clustering.

[14] A study of Rainfall over India Using Data Mining

In this paper [6], the authors have applied data mining techniques such as classification and clustering to analyze spatiotemporal data. The daily rainfall data is developed by Indian meteorological Department, Pune. The data is collected over the year 1951 to 2003 by all stations with minimum 90% data availability and other values are filled using interpolation. The authors have designed a system to handle climatic data. Algorithms are developed to extract climate data from the file which can be in the form of ASCII, NetCDF, and HDF format. All different format files needed to be converted into a single form such as ASCII format. Average rainfall over India is calculated for monsoon season and daily basis. Clustering is applied to the data and clusters are formed based on rainfall range. Cluster 1 depicts 0.1 to 3 mm rainfall, cluster 2 depicts 3 to 5 mm rainfall, cluster 3 depicts 5 to 10 mm rainfall, cluster 4 depicts 10 to 25 mm rainfall, and cluster 5 depicts rainfall greater than 25 mm. Classification is applied to the data with user defined thresholds as every region indicates different variation of rainfall. The approach can be extended by applying more data mining algorithms and more effective visualization of clusters.

III. CONCLUSION

This paper presented different approaches for handling and processing meteorological data. Data warehousing and distributed storage based frameworks are used for storing large amount of data. Data mining algorithms

such as Naïve Bayes, SVM and Kmeans are used for classifying rainfall events and creating clusters based on rainfall events. However storing large amount of data and applying data mining techniques on them is not enough we need distributed and efficient processing of the meteorological data. Hadoop mapreduce will process the data in distributed manner but it takes more time compare to Spark processing. In future, the researcher should focus on developing the system that enables user to store any kind of meteorological data into distributed storage, process the data and provide visualization of results on interactive interface.

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A Survey on Failure Prediction Techniques in Cloud Computing

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Abstract—The reliability of cloud service is a crucial issue for cloud service providers and the service users due to large scale demand of cloud computing services for the hosting applications at industrial level. There are two types of fault tolerance techniques namely reactive and proactive to address the issue of reliability. For the systems which require high availability of Virtual Machines the latter technique i.e. Proactive technique is used to make timely actions to reduce any losses. In Cloud Computing, using proactive fault tolerance techniques, issues such as Virtual Machine migration, Virtual Machine placement, Load balancing etc. can be addressed. In this survey paper, various methods are surveyed which predicts the failure in Cloud Systems and improves the reliability of Cloud Environment.

Keywords— *Cloud Computing Reliability, Virtual Machine Failure, Failure Prediction, Linear Regression, SVM, ANN, KNN, MING, LSTM, Random Forest*

IV. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing provides on-demand computing services such as applications, storage and processing power, typically over the internet and on a pay-as-you-go scheme. The services of cloud from cloud service provider can be rented rather than owning his / her own computing infrastructure or data centers.

Below are the three Cloud Service Models: [1]

SaaS:

SaaS or Software as a Service is a model that provides services of software and is available via a third party over the internet. No installations or downloads are required on your existing system with SAAS. Google G Suite, Dropbox, Microsoft Office 365, etc are common examples of SAAS.

IaaS:

Infrastructure as a Service or IaaS provides the provision of virtual computing resources on the cloud such as storage, networking hardware with continuous maintenance and support. Without installing hardware on their premises, businesses can opt for computing resources as per their requirement. The leading IaaS cloud service providers are Amazon Web Services, Microsoft Azure, and Google Compute Engine.

PaaS:

Platform as a Service or PaaS is a cloud-base where the user can develop, test and organize the different applications as per his business. PaaS simplifies the process to develop enterprise software. PAAS provides the virtual runtime

environment and gives a favorable platform for developing and testing applications. Examples of PaaS are Google App Engine and AWS Elastic Beanstalk are. PaaS is subscription based i.e. it gives flexible pricing options as per business requirements.

V. BACKGROUND

Reliability of Cloud systems lies when the cloud services are provided without any interruption. The cloud services are interrupted when there occurs a failure. Failure in cloud computing is as an event that occurs when there is deviation from intended service to delivered service. The failure in cloud systems can be one of the following. [2]

Network Faults:These are the faults that occur due to link failure or partition in network or loss of packet or packet corruption, destination failure, etc.

Physical Faults:These are the faults that occur in hardware. They can be fault in memory or fault in CPU and storage, fault in memory, etc.

Media Faults:These are the faults that occur when the media head crashes.

Processor Faults:These are the faults that occur in the processor because of crashes in the operating system.

Process Faults:These are the faults that occur when there is shortage of resources or there are software bugs, etc.

Service Expiry Faults:These are the faults that occur due to expiration of cloud services for the resource opted while using the application.

VI. LITERATURE SURVEY

To make the cloud computing environment reliable, one way is to predict the failure before it occurs and hence, we can make necessary steps such as VM migration or VM Load Balancing to avoid major loss. Failure prediction is also required for predictive maintenance as it has the ability to prevent failure incidents and thus, maintenance costs. Predictive maintenance anticipates failures and helps to take proactive actions. Many authors have used different machine learning algorithms to predict the failure. Basically, the prediction problem is classification problem. It results whether the current state of Cloud can result in failure or not. Based on historical pattern found that results in failure, future failures can be predicted in advance and major loss can be avoided.

Below are various techniques to predict the failure in the Cloud based environment.

- *Linear Regression and Support Vector Machine [3]*

HussainiAdamu [3] in his paper, compared two machine learning techniques to predict the failure in cloud system. The prediction is based on: Disk, DIMM, OS, Platform, HSV, CPU, and Others. The categories are based on these 7 groups. Two machine learning algorithms are used namely, Linear Regression Model (LRM) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) with a Gaussian kernel. Time is taken as the predictor variable and hardware failures are taken as the response variables. A linear regression model (LRM), takes into account the relationship between the predictor and response variable and is linear in nature. They obtained the prediction results using Linear Regression, SVM with Gaussian Kernel, and SVM with Polynomial Kernel. The results show that component failures and time shows correlation.

In the CPU failure group, the failures in the year 2006 was over 90, in 2007 the it decreased to over 40, and in 2008 a light decrease was there above 20. The DIMM failure group shows that in 2006 the number of failures was over 350, in 2007 there was a drastic drop to about 150 and in 2008 it decreased to about 100. The paper shows that the SVM outperforms the Linear Regression Model. The predicted result got by using these machine learning algorithms, shows that there exists a correlation between failure of components and time. That is, as time increases, failure rate decreases.

However, as the number of predicted year's increases, both models (especially the linear model) fails, thus consistently gives a zero value which is because of insufficient data obtained. Better results can be obtained if the data on which prediction is done spanned over many years. A failure prediction model should focus on accuracy and also on how easily the predicted result can be interpreted. Also, the prediction is not performed on large real time data of cloud environment.

- *Message Pattern Learning [4]*

PurvilBambharolia [4], defined a technique that consists of two different modules in his paper. One module predicts the failure using message logs that are passed between various components of cloud. The other module detects the failure after prediction. The proposed architecture for failure prediction is made up of these 3 phases:

(a) pre-process phase: it makes classification of input messages & then finds patterns of failure. In this phase, message patterns are derived from message logs that are recorded early. This phase has three steps: message classification, failure information extraction and generating message patterns. In message classification, the message gets divided into: timestamp, priority, message source, message text. Then the messages are classified on the basis of their similarity index. Thus, two messages fall into same group if they share many common words. In failure information extraction, the messages that are classified as Error, Critical, Alert or Emergency are considered that shows failure occurrence. The failure information is extracted once the

message classification results as a failure. In message patterns generation, message patterns are generated for prediction. A message pattern is a set of types of message present in the message window. It can a sequence of messages by either taking into account their order or ignoring their order.

(b) learning phase: it finds the probability of pattern that relates with failure. From the observed message pattern, the probability that a failure occurs in a certain period is estimated using Bayes' theorem using the message pattern dictionary. The probability is then updated in the message pattern dictionary.

(c) prediction phase: it compares the real time messages with the learned messages and predicts the possibility of failure. Failures are predicted by making usage of message patterns and probability that is in the pattern dictionary. With the input message pattern, the reference from the pattern dictionary is taken and the column that matches the input message pattern is taken. Then, calculations of probability for each type of message failure is done. If the probability for any message type of failure is greater than the threshold, it is taken as a sign of failure.

By improving the accuracy of the prediction model, the proposed technique can be enhanced. Advanced prediction models like ANN, recurrent neural networks, etc. can be used to improve the accuracy of the failure prediction. Also, this method can be further used to predict the downtime using prediction analysis.

- *ARIMA Model [5]*

Ajay Rawat [5] in his paper, used the ARIMA model to predict the failure of VMs. Using this model, prediction of VM failure is done on non-stationary failure trace. ARIMA i.e. auto-regressive moving average is applicable to both stationary as well as non-stationary data. ARIMA is denoted by (p, d, q) where $p, d, q \geq 0$ & $p, d, q \in \mathbb{Z}$. p is the order of autoregressive model, d is the degree of differencing, and q is the order of the MA model. For time-series of data, ARMA (p', d') model is given by following equation where $\alpha_0 = -1$, $\theta_0 = 1$, L is the lag operator, θ_i are the parameters of the MA part and α_i are the parameters of the autoregressive part of the model.

Box-Jenkins method is used to predict from historical time series data, the failure using a Failure Predictor Module (FPM). Non-stationary characteristics of Virtual machine failure is taken into consideration. The health info of 3000 VMs is used and observations are made from the weekly patterns of failure collected for 13 weeks. Using the Failure Predictor Module (FPM), the best-fitted ARIMA is found that has a minimum Bayesian information criterion (BIC) values & Akaike information criterion (AIC). Conversion of the non-stationary time series data to stationary data is done by log-transformed data's d order differencing. The Root mean square error (RMSE) is seen as 0.0457, Mean absolute error (MAE) as 0.0345, Mean absolute scaled error (MASE) as 0.6036. ACF and PACF plots are plotted to verify the residuals of ARIMA process for testing the accuracy of the prediction. No spikes were seen outside the relevant zone and the autocorrelation values tend to zero for both ACF and PACF plots. This shows

that remaining residuals are random. Therefore, accurate predictions are done using the FPM model.

One of the disadvantages of the ARIMA model is that it becomes unstable, both when changes in observations are made and when changes in model specification are made and is costly because it requires a large amount of data, and there is lacking convenient updating procedures and the fact that it must be estimated using nonlinear estimation procedures.

- *K-Nearest Neighbor, Artificial Neural Network, Random Forest and Support Vector Machine [6]*

Hussaini Adamu [6], in his paper, used four machine learning algorithms to develop a prediction-based model, that are: Support Vector Machines (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Random Forest (RF) to identify the overloading or underloading of the resources of hosts.

K-nearest neighbor (KNN) is a supervised machine learning model that uses training data to make classification of unknown instances. These instances are the known class labels and are grouped on their similar properties. KNN is a non-parametric method used to classify and its output is a class membership for different class groups (labels). Artificial Neural Network (ANN) of multiple layers have been used: an input layer, 2 hidden layers and an output layer. Four input neurons are taken in the input layer, $A = [A1, A2, A3, A4]$, three output neurons are taken in output layer, $B = [B1, B2, B3]$ and each hidden layer has 3 hidden neurons, $H = [H1, H2, H3]$. The neurons at each layer are connected to those of next layer. They are associated with a weight w_i which is calculated while training. The resultant output b_j is calculated with each training point a_i and w_i . The network weights are changed using the learning rate equal to 0.4 and momentum equal to 0.2. Random Forest (RF) is used to generate trees and categorize a new object from an input vector by penetrating the input vector on every tree in the forest. Each tree has a unit vote from the input vector that classifies them and the classification that has the maximum votes of all the trees in the forest is selected by the forests. Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a Machine Learning algorithm used by many of authors for prediction. Since, the complexity of SVM is less, it can accurately categorize the data which is linearly separable and is also used for the decision boundaries that are complex in nature. The hyperplanes are identified based on the classes that are grouped by SVM.

Their experimental results are compared that predicts the load using the above-mentioned models i.e. KNN, ANN, Random Forest, and SVM. The comparison results show that the Random Forest model achieves maximum accuracy as compared to SVM, KNN, and ANN. After Random Forest, ANN stood second in terms of maximum accuracy.

Although, reliability of Cloud Systems can be improved by combining these prediction approaches with fault-tolerant techniques. The approach is not tested on real data.

- *AdaBoost Hidden Markov model [7]*

Zhixin Li [7], in his paper, used the AdaBoost-Hidden Markov Model as a VM failure prediction method and

improved the reliability of VMs which eventually, improved the overall performance of the cloud system. Using AdaBoost influenced Hidden Markov Model, the relationship between the observation state and the hidden state of the Virtual Machine is found and the VM failure state is predicted. This method can be used with any cloud system for predicting the failure state of VMs, which eventually, improves the predictive ability of VM security state.

The security state of VM is difficult to predict that impact the potential security of the VM system. The proposed method makes use of HMM and solves this problem. The prediction of the observed state is done by AdaBoost algorithm. AdaBoost is an iterative algorithm and is used to combine multiple weak learners of linear regression to produce a strong learner. In HMM there is a hidden state and an observation state. The state transition probability is represented by A and observation probability is represented by B , and there is also an initial state π . Parameter λ is set as (A, B, π) . The collected observation state data of VMs is used by AdaBoost algorithm to predict the observation state of VM at the next step. Then, preprocessing of the observation state data is done to match the input of the HMM model. The parameter λ is set by the parameter learning in HMM model. Then after, prediction of the present state of VM is done and thereafter, the probability result of the failure of VM is obtained, and it can be known whether the VM is failed or not. The results show that the probability output of HMM is highly influenced by the value of 'c'. The smaller the value of c is, the more accurately it predicts the failure of VM.

However, there is a need in exploration of the relationship between the internal security state and the observation state of VM in the learning phase and prediction process. Also, the learning and prediction process can be further studied improved.

- *MING: Long Short-Term Memory & Random Forest [8]*

A node failure is caused by a variety of reasons and is reflected by many temporal and spatial signals. Qingwei Lin [8], in his paper, proposed a novel failure prediction model MING, that uses: a LSTM model to make predictions from the temporal data, a Random Forest model to make predictions from spatial data; a ranking model that ranks the nodes by their failure-proneness.

The temporal features are the attributes that represent a node's state in time (for example, IO throughput, resource usage, response delays, sensor values, etc.). Then can even be collected from the original sources (such as system event counts, log event counts, error or exception event counts, etc.). Spatial features define the global relationships among nodes in the form of explicit/implicit dependency. Deployment segment, load balance group, rack location, and update domain are some of the Spatial features.

For temporal features, LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) is used, and is a widely adopted deep neural network (DNN) model. It can balance between retaining the previous state and memorizing new information. LSTM captures the patterns behind the time-series data in a better manner and has proven to be successful in solving tasks such as machine translation and speech recognition. Bi-directional LSTM is used for the

time series data $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$; x_i is input vector of all temporal features on time i . The LSTM layer generates representation sequence $h_1, h_2, \dots, h_n$, that is passed to a fully connected dense layer. The output of this dense layer is 128×1 vector V_t . This vector is passed to a soft-max function, that is final layer of the DNN-based classifier. For spatial features, Random Forest technique is used, and is one of the most used classification techniques. It builds many decision trees during the training time and results the class of the voting result from the individual trees. Random Forest does splitting of the trees based on information gain; hence, it can better reflect the impact of discrete values. Here, an ensemble of total 128 trees are trained. The results $h_1, h_2, \dots, h_n$ are concatenated into a vector V_s and fed to a majority voting module which results into the final classification result.

When both of these features are used, MING is found to achieve an average F1-measure equal to 75.2%. When only the temporal features are used by predicting using the LSTM model, the average F1-measure can be seen to drop from 75.2% to 48.8%. When only the spatial features are used by making predictions using only the Random Forest model, the average F1-measure is seen to drop gradually from 75.2% to 57.1%. we also compare MING with the baseline approaches that are implemented using conventional classifiers including Logistic Regression, Random Forest, LSTM, and SVM. Also, the improvement in F1-measure of MING model over Logistic Regression, Random Forest, SVM and LSTM is 17.4%, 21.7%, 13.3%, and 14.6% respectively.

However, they have made trade-offs between precision and recall and gave more weightage to precision than recall. Also, LSTM is a bit more time consuming to train the model. Tradeoff has been made with the time consumption of model training.

VII. LITERATURE REVIEW SUMMARY

Following is the table representation of the techniques to predict the failures in cloud systems as discussed above. The authors of the papers surveyed are mentioned along with that paper's research gap.

TABLE 1 SUMMARY OF FAILURE PREDICTION TECHNIQUES

Author	Aim	Algorithm used	Research Gap
Hussaini Adamu, Bashir Mohammed, Ali Bukar Maina, Andrea Cullen [3]	To predict hardware failures in a real-time cloud environment to improve system availability.	Linear Regression Model, SVM	Prediction is based on a smaller number of features. Accuracy can be improved by other ML algorithms.
Purvil Bambharolia, Prajeet Bhavsar, Vivek Prasad [4]	To solve proactive management of failures by failure prediction and detection	Message pattern learning, Bayes' theorem	Accuracy can be improved by using ANN, RNN. Time consuming.

Author	Aim	Algorithm used	Research Gap
Ajay Rawat, Rama Sushil, Amit Agarwal & Afzal Sikander [5]	The prediction of virtual machine failure based on the time series stochastic model	ARIMA	Based on non-correlated data. Not used real cloud environment
Anju Bala, Inderveer Chana [6]	Aims at analyzing the problem of load prediction by comparing the performance of various ML algorithms.	ANN, SVM, KNN, Random Forest	Accuracy can be improved by combination of various ML techniques.
Zhixin Li, Lei Liu, Degang Kong [7]	To improve the reliability of VMs and overall performance of cloud platforms by focusing on VM hidden security state	Hidden Markov Model	Observation state of VM is valued only by load, Relationship between observation state of VM and internal security state needs to be explored.
Qingwei Lin, Ken Hsieh [8]	Predicts the failure of a node in cloud system based on historical data.	MING: LSTM + Random forest	Hyperparameters for both models can be optimized, LSTM takes more time

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a survey of various prediction techniques for Failure Prediction in the cloud environment is done. After evaluating well known techniques, it is clear which methods should be used in which kind of environment. Random forest can be used in place of LR and SVM. ARIMA model can be used where there is stationary data. Ada-boost Hidden Markov Model can be used to predict the hidden security state of Virtual Machines. Of all the methods seen here, LSTM is seen to be the best model to predict the failures in the cloud environment. Though, the training is time consuming as compared to other models. Also, the idea behind the partition of data based on temporal and spatial features leads to better prediction of failure in the cloud systems. With arrival of new techniques, the papers are referred here and it is seen that latest techniques can perform better than old techniques.

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